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**EXPERIMENTAL STUDY AND MULTISCALE NUMERICAL SIMULATION
OF THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF CRACKS IN VISCOELASTIC
MATERIALS: APPLICATION TO BILINGA (*NAUCLEADIDEERRICHI*)**

By

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Abstract

The mechanical behaviour of local wood specie (Bilinga) in the south west region of Cameroon under the bending loading condition during the rainy and dry seasons are studied. The objective of this study was to determine the response of the wood (Bilinga) under mechanical stress in both weather conditions and also to study the crack initiation and its propagation of this wood of any of the species using the finite element analysis and compare its result using the stochastic model.

To meet these objectives, the three-point flexural tests were used to determine the mechanical properties of the wood studied. A finite element software ANSYS workbench 2020 R1 is used for the numerical simulation on macroscopic level by one of the most recent technologies called the Smart crack growth which was introduced from the 2019 version. The geometry was modelled in SolidWorks (2016) with initial cracks of 4mm and 8mm introduced in each sample and imported to ANSYS work which has all the tools to perform linear fracture and further analyses. The stress intensity factor (SIF) determines the fracture toughness of the material which is subjected to linear-elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) where the stress intensify variable is represented as K_{IC} . Fatigue crack growth has been modelled using Paris' law. The

crack growth was simulated based on Mode I crack specimen with initial crack length of 4mm and 8mm respectively. The stochastic quasi3D-modeling of crack growth on micro scale used for comparing the crack growth rate using the heterogeneous material approach and taking into account the microstructure and fracture mechanism of the Bilinga wood. After analysing 10 samples each of Bilinga from the rainy and the dry season, results for Bilinga of the rainy season shows an elasticity modulus of 8.828 MPa as compared to that of the dry season which is 6.7415 MPa, for the stress intensity factor, Bilinga of the rainy season was 16,347 MPa \sqrt{m} as compared to that of the dry season which is 9,478 MPa \sqrt{m} . For the energy release rate, Bilinga of the rainy season was 134428 J/m² as compared to that of the dry season which is 145575 J/m² and for the rupture energy, Bilinga of the rainy season was 1875.12 kJ/m² as compared to that of the dry season which is 1276.25 J/m². For the moisture content, Bilinga of the rainy season was 14% as compared to that of the dry season which is 12% and for the density, Bilinga of the rainy season was 780kg/m³ as compared to that of the dry season which is 680 kg/m³.

The result of stochastic modelling of the crack growth in the array of cracks and pores of characteristic size shows that the simulation is close to FE-modelling results. Therefore, stochastic simulation of crack growth in the wood at mesoscale and micro scale shows the lower local stress intensity factors and slower crack growth due to existence of the scale-time hierarchy. The crack growth rate at macroscale equals $v_{cr} = 0.845-0.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$ which corresponds to macroscopic stress intensity variable K_{IC} .

Keywords: Viscoelastic, cracks, mechanical behaviour, Bilinga, FE-modelling, Stochastic modelling, structural approach.

Table 1: Abbreviations

K_{IC}	Stress intensify factor
FEA	Finite Element analysis
LEFM	Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics
NLFM	Non-Linear Fracture Mechanics
FPZ	Fracture Process Zone
SIF	Stress Intensity Factor
M.C.	Moisture Content
BI-R-A-NC is the same as BI-R-A	Bilinga rainy season of specie A with no initial crack
BI-D-B-NC is the same as BI-D-B	Bilinga dry season of specie B with no initial crack
BI-R-A-C4	Bilinga rainy season of specie A with a crack of 4mm
BI-D-B-C4	Bilinga dry season of specie B with a crack of 4mm
BI-R-A-C8	Bilinga rainy season of specie A with a crack of 8mm
BI-D-B-C8	Bilinga dry season of specie B with a crack of 8mm

1 Introduction

Bilinga is considered one of the most valuable woods because of its unusual strength and resistance, excellent flexibility and decorative appearance. It is widely used in marine and onshore construction. It is used for planed veneer, interior and exterior cladding panels, joinery, sleepers, posts, carpentry and piling structures of piers, wharves, platforms, window sills, various furniture and parquet. It is used for decorative finishing of interiors and exteriors of premises, terraces and garden objects; it is excellent for covering of floors in residential and industrial premises, vehicles and containers. Due to the high tannin and natural oil content in the wood. Bilinga is resistant to the most diverse weather and climatic conditions, sunlight and seawater. This is why it is excellent for the construction of bridges and seagoing vessels, especially ply boats and their decks [1].

Bilinga wood is very strong and hard, it surpasses oak wood in all technical parameters except the aspect of splitting and resistance to impact loads. Its density at standard humidity can range from 740 kg/m³ to 810 kg/m³. Bilinga is highly water- and fire-resistant, so it is suitable for use in a variety of temperature and humidity ranges. It is considered one of the most resistant of the existing breeds, as it is practically unaffected by attacks from insects, termites and even sea grinders, and also resists the appearance of fungi on its surface also [1].

The mechanical behaviour of this wood is quite complex due to its anisotropic nature [1]. The fracture behaviour also is commonly accepted as a quasi-brittle behaviour in which a softening zone called Fracture Process Zone (FPZ) exists ahead of the crack tip [2]. However, micro-cracks, which can propagate and cause failure, are commonly found in all timber structures. Failure is principally a result of fatigue. Fatigue is the process of progressive localized irreversible change in a material, and may culminate in cracks or complete fracture if conditions that are initiated or propagated on the process persist [1]. The viscoelastic behaviour of wood under varying moisture phenomenon as well as the coupling phenomenon between the temperature and the moisture transfer in this wood material is often explained [3]. However, most models do not consider the crack growth in the structure. Combining mechanical solicitation like fatigue, overload, or creep loading and environmental actions like hydro or temperature will play an important role in the growth of these micro-cracks in structural materials [4]. To determine the behaviour of cracks in wooden beams, many numerical methods are used to characterize the stress around the crack tip which one of them is the J-integral developed by J Rice in 1968 [5]. For elastic and viscous-elastic material the SIF approach of NLFM could be used. The first part of this paper presents the material and method used in this work. The mathematical formulation of J-integral to determine the stress intensity factor around the crack tip, the energy release rate calculated using the result from the laboratory experiment with respect to mode I specimen is presented in the second part. In addition, the Kelvin Voigt Model was used to model the viscoelastic material [6]. The third part of the paper presents the FE numerical modelling of the wooden bulk deformation under the three-point bend

loading at the macroscale, and the stochastic modelling of crack growth by the mechanism of crack and pores coalescence on the microscale of Bilinga wood material.

2 Materials

2.1 Primary Material (Bilinga)

The figure 1 below presents the raw material and the prepared material used for the analysis and the characterisation.

Figure 1: Sample piece: (a) Raw material, (b) Prepared sample for mechanical characterization

2.2 Flexural testing machine

The flexural testing machine used in carryout the three-point bending test as seen on the figure 2 below. It is equipped with a camera that records every detail such as fracture appearance and breakage point. Universal hydraulic grips with a set of wedge members are used to carry out bending test, compression test, etc. High stiffness frame with minimum deflection at maximum load (0.9 mm). Upper/lower rollers: 160 mm. Ram travel: 110 mm.

Figure 2: Flexural testing machine of 200 kN loaded with sample piece

2.3 Electronic Balance of type XPR5003S

The figure 3 below represents an electronic balance of type XPR5003S. It is used to take measurement like the mass of the samples, moisture content, etc. Its maximum capacity is 5.1 kg, readability of 1 mg and with a minimum weight (USP, 0.1, typical) 6 g.

Figure 3: Electronic Balance type XPR5003S [7]

2.4 Electric Oven

The figure 4 below represents an electric oven. It is used in drying the wood in order to prepare it for physical characterization. It has a power rating of **2.0-2.2 kWh**, which means its consumption is between 2,000 and 2,200 watts for every hour.

Figure 4: Electric Oven dryer [7]

3 Methods

3.1 Material Preparation

A selection of Bilinga wood was done in the midst of rainy season **with a temperature range of between 24-28°C** with 1889mm of accumulated precipitation in the month of

August. It was termed BI -R-A-NC (Bilinga rainy season of specie A without initial crack), while the same specie of wood was harvested in the dry season i.e. in the month of February with a temperature range between 28-34°C and with 167mm of accumulated precipitation. It was also termed BI-D-B-NC (Bilinga dry season of specie B without initial crack). 10 specimens were prepared for each specie for characterization. In this paper, the specimen preparation is subjected to rigorous and precise process such as an accurate alignment of the specimen in the tangential and longitudinal directions of wood, a check on the exactness of the length, width and thickness of all the samples of both species is done. For the physical characterization, the dimension of the specimens was (20 × 20 × 360 mm and 20 × 20 × 20 mm). Specimens were stored into an electric oven for 24 hours to attain different Relative humidity; the oven was conditioned under a constant temperature (200°C). The equilibrium moisture content of the specimen was obtained when its weight between 2 days did not change, with a reasonable tolerance of (0.05 g). For the investigation of the crack propagation, an initial crack of 4mm and 8mm was induced on each specimen on each of the specie then was simulated with specimens without any initial crack.

3.2 Physical Properties

These studies were carried out at ENSET Douala in the Forestry Engineering laboratory. This part is about studying the variability of density. These characters are essential to judge the quality of the wood and its classification for a given use.

3.2.1 Moisture content

The oven drying method is the standard way of determining wood moisture content. With this method, 10 specimens of each species of wood measuring 20 × 20 × 20 mm were initially weighed on an electronic scale balance and then dried in an oven at 103°C ± 2°C for 24 hours. Drying continues and measurement is taken until all the specimens completely dried off i.e. (when no further weight loss occurs). The formula below is used in determining the water content [8]:

$$MC = \frac{m - m_0}{m_0} \cdot 100\% \quad (1)$$

m is the average of the mass of specimen before submerged in water while m_0 is the average of the mass of the dried specimen.

3.2.2 Density

In order to determine the density, the 10 specimens for each specie were submerged into distilled water. To determine the volume (V_s), Archimedes method was used which consists of weighing an empty container of water on a scale and recording its mass $M1$ then immersing each of the specie inside the distilled water for at least 4 hours and then taking the mass gain to have $M2$ and in the end differentiate between the two masses as indicated by the equation $V_s = M1 - M2$ [7]

3.2.3 Mechanical Properties

3.2.3.1 Determination of the mechanical strength

In this study, the woods studied are of section (20 × 20 × 360 mm) with moisture content of 12% water oven dry and 14% water oven dry. The tests were carried out on 10 specimens per specie. The flexural modulus of elasticity E_f (MPa) and the energy release rate G (J / m^2) were carried out according to standard N F B 51-008. Standard N F B 51-008.

Table 2: Characteristics of samples for mechanical properties

Origin of Sample	Types of test	Number of samples	Dimension (mm)	geometry
Bi -R-A-NC	Flexural	10	360x20x20	longitudinal
Bi -D-B-NC	Flexural	10	360x20x20	longitudinal

The figure 5 below represents the three-point bending procedure used for the determination of the mechanical strength of the Bilinga.

Figure 5: Simple supported beam under study

Procedure

The principle of the simple bending test is to determine the maximum load at which failure will occur on a material sample on two supports with an application at mid-distance of the supports to one constant speed on a sample. The load is applied continuously to a speed equal to 2mm/min. The simultaneous measurement of the loads and displacement were taken till rupture of the sample.

3.2.4 The modulus of elasticity (E_f)

The modulus of elasticity (E_f) calculated on the principles of the N standard FB 51-016 (1987) [8]. It is a function of the load, the displacement and the coefficient of rigidity. The recording of the "force-deflection" curve makes it possible to calculate inside of the linear zone the flexural stiffness K .

$$K = \frac{\Delta F}{\Delta S} \quad (2)$$

$$E_f = \frac{L^2}{4bh^3} K \quad (3)$$

3.2.5 Energy of rupture:

Curves were obtained for the displacement during the three-point bending of the two species having a notch $a_1 = 4$ mm, $a_2 = 8$ mm. For graphical calculation, tools like Origin Pro 2019b were used. It allows the calculation of the area using the option (analysis, calculation, integral). The results obtained are in (N × mm), meanwhile, to obtain the values of J (energy of rupture), a simple division over the thickness of the sample piece is recommended ($e = 20$ mm) times the depth of the notch, which gives the rate of energy release G in (Joule/mm²) [8].

3.2.6 Stress intensity factor

It has shown that in mode I the value of K_{IC} can be determined from the energy refund rate. G_{IC} (Specific energy of rupture or energy of propagation crack) by the formula below: [9]

$$K_{ic} = \sqrt{E_f \cdot G_{ic}} \quad (4)$$

Where K_{IC} is the stress intensity factor and E_f is the elasticity modulus.

3.2.7 Numerical modelling

In order to analyse cracked timber structures under real service conditions, the moisture content level in wood during the loading must be considered in the framework of fracture mechanic. On the other hand, the main problem is the coupling between the hydride state and the mechanical state in the material, as well as the coupling between the configuration with and without the crack propagation. In this paper, in order to have a better comprehension of the loaded structure behaviour, the modelling of the cracked structure taking into account the moisture variation is proposed and studied [10].

3.2.8 J Integral

Consider a homogeneous body of linear or nonlinear elastic material free of body forces and subjected to a two-dimensional deformation field (plane strain, generalized plane stress, anti-plane strain) so that all stresses σ_{ij} depend only on two Cartesian coordinates $x_1 (= x)$ and $x_2 (= y)$. A straight crack is a limiting case that can define the strain-energy

$$\text{density } W \text{ by } W = W_{(x,y)} = W(\varepsilon) = \int_0^{\varepsilon} \sigma_{ij} d\varepsilon_{ij}. \quad (5)$$

The figure 6 below shows a consideration of a crack tip with notch of any sample under mechanical loading.

Figure 6: Crack tip with notch [10]

Where $\varepsilon = [\varepsilon_{ij}]$ is the infinitesimal strain tensor. Now we consider the integral defined by:

$$J = \int_{\Gamma} \left(W dy - T \cdot \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} ds \right). \quad (6)$$

Here Γ is a curve surrounding the notch tip, the integral being evaluated in a contra clockwise sense starting from the lower notch surface and continuing along the path Γ to the upper surface. T is the traction vector defined to the out-ward normal along Γ $T_i = \sigma_{ij} n_j$ U is the displacement vector, and ds is an element of arc length along Γ . To prove path independence, consider any closed curve Γ enclosing an area A in a two-dimensional deformation field, free of body forces. An application of Green's theorem [5] gives:

$$\int_{\Gamma} \left(W dy - T_i \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} ds \right) = \int_{\Gamma} \left[\frac{\partial W}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\sigma_{ij} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} \right) \right] dx dy \quad (7)$$

Differentiating the strain-strain density

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial W}{\partial x} &= \frac{\partial W}{\partial \varepsilon_{ij}} \cdot \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{ij}}{\partial x} = \sigma_{ij} \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{ij}}{\partial x} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{ij} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \right] \\ &= \sigma_{ij} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\sigma_{ij} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\sigma_{ij} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} \right) \left(\text{since } \frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}}{\partial x_j} = 0 \right)$$

The area integral vanishes identically, and thus

$$\int_{\Gamma} \left(W dy - T \cdot \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} ds \right) = 0 \quad (9)$$

But $T = 0$ $dy = 0$

Clearly, by taking Γ close to the notch tip we can make the integral depend only on it, particularly the path may be shrunk to the tip Γ_i of a smooth ended notch and since $T=0$ therefore,

$$J = \int_{\Gamma_i} W dy \quad (10)$$

3.2.9 Numerical simulation

The size of a flaw in any material is an important variable in fracture analysis, as is the stress on the flaw and the fracture toughness of the material, which replaces material strength in fracture calculations. The stress intensity factor (SIF) determines the fracture toughness of a material subject to linear-elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM); the SIF variable represented as K_{IC} . For elastic-plastic fracture mechanics (EPFM), fracture toughness determined by the energy required to grow a crack, represented by JIC, also known as the J-integral parameter. Fatigue crack growth modelled by using Paris' law as seen below [11-14]:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C (\Delta K_I)^m \quad (11)$$

The numerical simulation has done with the help of a finite element software ANSYS workbench 2020R1. With the help of the most recent technology of ANSYS workbench call Smart crack growth that has introduced from the 2019 version of ANSYS. The geometry had modelled in SolidWorks with initial cracks of 4mm and 8mm introduced in each sample and imported to ANSYS workbench and further analysis with ANSYS that has all the tools to perform linear fracture, all geometry data have found in table below.

I. Geometry

The geometry was modelled using SOLIDWORKS 2017, the solid based on the characteristic of sample used for the experimental study. The file format and geometry characteristic are found in table 3 below.

Table 3. Geometrical information for solid model in ANSYS

File Type	IGES
Length Unit	Millimetres
Element Control	Program Controlled
Display Style	Body Colour
Bounding Box	
Length X	360. mm
Length Y	20. mm
Length Z	20. mm
Properties	
Volume	1.4393e+005 mm ³
Mass	1.1298 kg
Scale Factor Value	1.

Initial cracks of 4mm and 8mm were introduced to models and saved in IDES file format where it can be open and read in Ansys.

3.3 Meshing generation

Because of the existence of crack tip singularity, the usual elements surrounding the crack tip should be generated refined mesh in order to derive reliable stress intensity factor results. Figure 7 below shows the Bilinga wood of any of the specie placed in meshing solid in ANSYS workbench that requires the body part structure with cracks that should be meshed with tetrahedron elements, while other bodies without cracks can be set arbitrary element types. Meanwhile, the crack mesh generation settings of Work bench are more convenient than settings under ANSYS classic analysis environment, because under Work bench environment, mesh refinement of the crack tip is automatically generated, after accomplishment of mesh generation for the whole body.

Figure 7: Meshing solid in ANSYS workbench

3.4 Summary

SMART simulation is the latest in a long line of ANSYS innovations designed to solve the critical issue of crack initiation growth and fracture in product design. Meshing around the crack tip after each iteration concentrates the computing power where it is needed most, making SMART simulations faster and easier to scale up for larger projects. Using UMM (unstructured meshing method) for meshing eliminates costly pre-processing time and produces a test mesh that is just as accurate as a time-consuming hex mesh [15-16]. The algorithm below gives the different step to carryout crack propagation on ANSYS workbench

3.5 Rupture Energy

The fracture energy is proportionally reversed to the notch depth.

3.6 Energy release rate

Energy release rate can be calculated from the experimental data.

3.7 Stress intensity factor K_{Ic}

The stress intensity factor is a parameter that amplified the magnitude of the applied stress that includes the geometrical parameter (load). The stress intensity in any mode situation is directly proportional to the applied load of the material

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Physical Properties

4.1.1 Moisture content of wood of specie BI-R-A-NC and specie BI-D-B-NC

Figure 8 below shows the moisture content of the Bilinga wood in both the rainy and the dry season. It can be observed that south West Bilinga harvested in the dry season has a higher relative moisture content which is 14% than the one harvested during the rainy season, 12%.

Figure 8: Relative moisture Content

4.1.2 Density

Figure 9 below shows the density of the Bilinga wood in both the rainy and the dry seasons. The density of both species was determined and presented on the table below.

Figure 9: Density chart for species

The one which is harvested in the rainy season has a higher density value than the one harvested during the dry season.

4.2 Mechanical Properties

4.2.1 Elastic behaviour of wood

The curve on Fig.10 represents specie of type BI-R-A-NC with no initial crack and specimens with initial crack of 4mm and 8mm.

Figure 10: Force displacement curve for Bilinga BI-R-A

The curve on Fig.11 represents specie of type BI-D-B-NC with no initial crack and specimens with initial crack of 4mm and 8mm.

Figure 11: Force displacement curve for Bilinga BI-D-B

The curve on Fig. 12 represents the displacement versus force for the two different specie Bilinga wood probes. It shows that the deformation curves are same.

Figure 12: Meshing solid in ANSYS workbench

It can be noticed that both species of Bilinga i.e. in the dry and rainy seasons, with or without initial crack, show no variation in elasticity when they are meshed together.

4.2.2 Mechanical Properties.

The table 4 below presents the results of Bilinga in the rainy season (specie A) and Bilinga of the dry season (specie B).

Table 4: Mechanical properties and crack parameters from experimental result

Region	Number of sample	Modulus of elasticity MPa	Stress intensity factor $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$	Energy release rate(J/m^2)	Energy of Rupture (kJ/m^2)
BI-R-A	10	8.828	16,347	134428	1875.12
BI-D-B	10	6.7415	9,478	145575	1276.25

From the above table, it can be seen that the Bilinga in the rainy season has a higher elasticity modulus, stress intensity factor and a higher energy of rupture than the Bilinga of the dry season.

3.2.3 Crack length displacement against time

Figure 13 below, shows the crack length displacement against time line for the meshing of both species. So the crack tip velocity calculated as 0,845 mm/s.

Figure 13: Crack length against time

4.2.3 Equivalent stress

Equivalent stress considers different effects resulting from multi axial residual stress states (see Fig.14) for the both species in both seasons. This means that in 1sec, Bilinga that is exposed in the average weather condition in Cameroon can support a maximum stress of 308.18 MPa

Figure 14: Equivalent plotted curve for stress against time

4.2.4 Strain energy

Strain energy is a type of potential energy that is stored in a structural member as a result of elastic deformation. Figure 15 represents a time dependence curve of the strain energy.

Figure 15: Strain energy

This means that in 1sec, Bilinga that is exposed in the average weather condition in Cameroon can release in a second a maximum energy release rate of 54.069 J/m²

4.2.5 Crack growth rate

The crack propagation was simulated base on numerical data collected from laboratory experiment and the simulation was based on 6 contours and the result is represented on figure 16. The crack growth velocity could be calculated as $v_{cr} \sim 0.90 \text{ mm/sec} = 0.9 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m/sec}$.

Figure 16: Crack growth rate

Figure 17, below, represent the growth rate of crack with respect to time: the graph shows that the crack starts at zero, increases progressively at 0.333 and then propagate to a length of 0.35mm. This explains the resistance of the material studied. The stress concentration on the crack tip was also determined and presented on the figures 17 (a) and (b) below.

Figure 17: (a): Stress concentrated on crack tip; **(b):** Stress concentrated at crack tip

4.3 Structural Stochastic Modelling of Crack Growth

4.3.1 Micro mechanism of fracture for Bilinga wood

The FE-modelling based on isotropic solid concept does not take into account the structural heterogeneities and anisotropy of the properties of a natural material such as wood, even soft wood [17-20]. It is necessary to verify the structural modelling so as to estimate the key fracture parameters. The microstructure of Bilinga wood is well known by the several museum researches. We use images of the microstructure of tangential section of Opepe, Bilinga (Lat. *Nauclea diderrichii*), by Hans Beeckman, Royal Museum of Central Africa, Belgium, and cross-section by M.E. Bakker, Naturalis Biodiversity Centre (Figure 19, a), and Frances Whinder & Peter Gasson, Royal Botanic Gardens – Kew (Figure 19, b).

In general, the wood is loaded crosswise to the growth of the fibres trough

the tangential section because of high strength and processing technology reasons. So the crack growth in the cross section will be faster than in the tangential section of the wood due to big pores (up to $\varnothing 200 \mu\text{m}$) coalescence. In the case of the tangential section, however, cracks will be slower because of the time needed to have the crack to be form and for it to grow, which will also subsequently merge into the main crack (see Figure 19). The size of crack will start from 50 to 200 μm (see Fig.19, b). The vessels (micro pores) size is about 10 μm here.

Figure 18: Microstructure images of Bilinga wood (tangential section): a) 3.0 mm wide, b) 800 μm .

4.3.2 Results of Stochastic Modelling of the Crack Growth on Micro scale

Although LEFM does not provide for the consideration of levels in a solid, the multi scale description must be introduced for at least a brief theory of crack dynamics. For the verification of the crack growth rate by structural multi scale stochastic modelling is necessary to qualitatively and quantitatively evaluate the fracture mechanism of wood [19]. Considering the first mode i.e. mode I, which is the (opening mode) and applying on the bending and loading process on the sample, where the external normal stress is perpendicular to crack [21].

Figure 19: Microstructure images of Bilinga wood (cross section): a) 2.0 mm wide, b) 6.0 mm wide.

For the Bilinga wood, the stochastic fracture modelling based on the mechanism of viscous coalescence of pores (vessels) by the small crack growth across the fibres was used [21]. Scheme of multi scale quasi3D-modeling presented on Fig.20 below.

A scale-time hierarchy according the proposed system-structural approach [22-24] reflects the dependence of the local approach by LEFM relation:

$$\delta_c = \frac{2 \cdot K_{IC}}{\pi \cdot \sigma_c^2}; \tau_c = \frac{\delta_c}{c}.$$

Here c – is the elastic wave velocity in direction of loading, for wood $c \approx 4000$ m/sec. δ_c, τ_c – is the size and time of the scale, (12) mesoscale the $\tau_c \sim 10^{-5}$ sec, and for micro scale $\tau_c \sim 10^{-7}$ sec.

However, the fracture mechanism at micro scale would be different and described by short crack growth law. The large variability of crack growth rates at different scales is a result of micro structural influence on the local crack driving force. To accurately do prediction of the crack growth rate on microscale, a local rather than a far field driving force must be used. The question is that for the wood, the growth patterns of short cracks have not been sufficiently investigated, and we have to assume the mechanism of growth and coalescence of micro pores based on images of micro structural sections (Fig.18-19).

Figure 20: Scheme of crack growth modelling based on multi scale quasi3D-modeling: a) FE-model realized by Smart Crack ANSYS approach (main crack at macro scale); b) stochastic modelling of main crack growth (crack branching at mesoscale ~ 0.1 mm); and c) stochastic modelling of crack tip coalescence with micro pores (wood vessels on micro scale $\sim 1 \div 10$ μm).

The results of main crack growth visualization on mesoscale by the mechanism of short cracks coalescence is presented on Figure 21 below.

Figure 21: Crack growth from the pore of 20 μm radius on meso scale

The calculated area is 1200 \times 1200 μm . Distance between the cracks is 25 μm . A normal distribution of the cracks with a standard deviation of 1 μm and K_I , $\text{MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{-0.5}$: a) 35.0, b) 36.0, c) 37.0, d) 38.0 (see Table 5). The micro pores coalescence mechanism used for simulation of short crack growth at micro scale (see Figure 22).

Figure 22: Crack growth by micro pores (5-10 μm radius) coalescence from the crack tip on microscale.

The calculated area is $760 \times 380 \mu\text{m}$. Distance between the cracks is $10 \mu\text{m}$. A normal distribution of the cracks with a standard deviation of $1 \mu\text{m}$ and K_I , $\text{MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{-0.5}$: a) 53.0, b) 54.0, c) 55.0, d) 56.0 (see Table 5).

The calculated crack growth rates at different local stress intensities K_I used by stochastic model is shown on Table 5.

Table 5. Crack growth rate v_{cr} calculated by stochastic model

Scale	Meso ($\delta_c \sim 100 \mu\text{m}$)				Micro ($\delta_c \sim 10 \mu\text{m}$)			
	K_I , $\text{MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{-0.5}$	35.0	36.0	37.0	38.0	53.0	54.0	55.0
v_{cr} , m/sec	$1.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$

Therefore, stochastic simulation of crack growth in the wood at mesoscale and micro scale shows a lower local stress intensity factor and slower crack growth due to existence of the scale-time hierarchy. The crack growth rate at macro scale is $v_{cr} = 0.845 - 0.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$ which corresponds to macroscopic K_{IC} .

5 Conclusion

The purpose of this research was to consider a model of Bilinga wooden beam in function of the different seasons and to study the mechanical influence and the effects of crack and its propagation using a finite element program ANSYS. The same species of wood from the same region of Cameroon harvested in two different seasons were used for the experimentation to find out if their different seasons will influence their mechanical properties. The simulation was calibrated and modified based on experimental result. Finding out the critical energy rational value for which the fracture mode to match with available experimental result and material properties was one of the main points of focus. A study was carried out in order to compare the cracks of the different samples with an initial crack of 4mm on the specimens of the two species with that of initial crack of 8mm also applied on the specimens on the two species. The rate of crack growth was verified with the application of micro scale by structural stochastic modelling. This method is used in order to analyse the crack growth of timber structures under environmental conditions in which moisture effect is integrated into the Fracture Process Zone (FPZ), so that the coupling between the mechanical behaviour of wood and the crack growth process can be expressed. The stochastic simulation of crack growth in the wood at mesoscale and micro scale shows a lower local SIF and slower crack growth due to existence of the scale-time hierarchy. Crack growth rate at the macro scale corresponds to non-local macroscopic SIF. The virtues of Bilinga wood in industrial application cannot be over emphasize therefore

further research of this wood mixed with composite or synthetic material will be of great gain to its usage.

Data Availability

The data used to support the findings of this study are available and can be gotten from the corresponding author upon request.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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